

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Supplemental Figure S1. Quantile-quantile plots (Q-Q plot) of $-\log_{10}$ of P -values resulting from the genome-wide association analyses of production and conformation traits. Deviations from the slope line correspond to loci that deviate from null hypothesis of no association. λ = genomic inflation factor; MKG = milk yield; FKG = fat yield; PKG = protein yield; MEY = milk energy yield; BCS = body condition score; BD = body depth; CW = chest width; DCH = dairy character; STAT = stature; UD = udder depth

Supplemental Figure S2. Quantile-quantile plots (Q-Q plot) of $-\log_{10}$ of P -values resulting from the genome-wide association analyses of diseases traits for lactation numbers 1 to 3. Derivations from the slope line correspond to loci that deviate from null hypothesis of no association. λ = genomic inflation factor; KET = ketosis; MF = milk fever; DA = displaced abomasum, META = all metabolic diseases

Supplemental Figure S3. Manhattan plots showing $-\log_{10}(P)$ of GWAS for metabolic disease traits displaced abomasum (DA), ketosis (KET), milk fever (MF) and all metabolic diseases (META) in second lactation. Red line indicates genome-wide threshold at $-\log_{10}(P) = 5.95$, blue line indicates suggestive threshold at $-\log_{10}(P) = 4.64$

Supplemental Table S1. Definitions of conformation traits according to International Committee for Animal Recording (ICAR, 2018).

Trait	Definition	Scale
Body condition score (BCS)	The covering of fat over the tail head and rump	1 (poor) - 9 (grossly fat)
Body depth (BD)	Distance between top of spine and bottom of barrel at last rib	1 (shallow) - 9 (deep)
Chest width (CW)	Measured from the inside surface between the top of the front legs	1 (narrow) - 9 (wide)
Dairy character (DCH)	Sharpness at withers	1 (round) - 9 (very sharp)
Stature (STAT)	Measured from the top of the spine in between hips to ground	Measured in cm
Udder depth (UD)	The distance from the lowest part of the udder floor to the hock	1 (deep) - 9 (shallow)

Supplemental Table S2. Genetic correlations between production traits, body size measurements and metabolic disease traits in first lactation. Standard errors in parenthesis

	KET	DA	META
MKG	0.212 (0.077)	0.194 (0.056)	0.220 (0.062)
FKG	0.190 (0.078)	0.133 (0.062)	0.203 (0.061)
PKG	0.159 (0.079)	0.224 (0.057)	0.189 (0.061)
MEY	0.137 (0.061)	0.111 (0.061)	0.113 (0.071)
BCS	-0.470 (0.102)	-0.255 (0.061)	-0.417 (0.073)
BD	-0.054 (0.091)	0.102 (0.062)	0.043 (0.081)
CW	-0.219 (0.103)	-0.080 (0.072)	-0.186 (0.082)
DCH	0.469 (0.091)	0.269 (0.062)	0.459 (0.074)
STAT	0.234 (0.090)	0.172 (0.061)	0.242 (0.071)
UD	-0.060 (0.080)	-0.028 (0.062)	-0.036 (0.071)

Supplemental Table S3. Identified significant SNPs for production traits

BTA	SNP name	Position SNP (Mb)	Trait
3	ARS-BFGL-NGS-64215	15.47	MKG
5	BTB-01278164	88.36	MKG, FKG, PKG, MEY
5	Hapmap51546-BTA-109428	91.20	FKG
5	ARS-BFGL-NGS-108617	91.39	FKG
5	Hapmap33512-BTA-158274	91.85	FKG
5	ARS-BFGL-NGS-95906	93.49	FKG
5	Hapmap41349-BTA-74576	94.17	FKG
5	ARS-BFGL-NGS-20806	94.35	FKG
6	Hapmap23522-BTC-047379	85.49	MKG, PKG, MEY
6	Hapmap30192-BTC-072881	85.55	MKG, PKG, MEY
6	Hapmap54336-rs29010419	86.40	PKG
6	ARS-BFGL-NGS-118182	86.86	MKG, FKG, MEY
6	BTB-00133212	86.92	MKG, FKG, PKG, MEY
6	ARS-BFGL-NGS-17376	87.09	MKG, MEY
6	BTB-01654826	87.16	MKG, FKG, PKG, MEY
6	BTA-68275-no-rs	87.27	MKG, FKG, PKG, MEY
11	ARS-BFGL-NGS-31097	103.24	MKG, PKG
14	ARS-BFGL-NGS-34135	0.49	MKG, FKG, PKG
14	ARS-BFGL-NGS-94706	0.51	MKG, FKG, PKG
14	ARS-BFGL-NGS-4939	0.61	MKG, FKG, PKG
14	Hapmap52798-ss46526455	0.73	MKG, FKG, PKG
14	ARS-BFGL-NGS-107379	0.86	MKG, FKG, PKG
14	UA-IFASA-8997	1.00	MKG, FKG, PKG
14	Hapmap25384-BTC-001997	1.02	MKG, FKG
14	Hapmap24715-BTC-001973	1.04	MKG, FKG
14	ARS-BFGL-NGS-26520	1.18	MKG, FKG
14	Hapmap30374-BTC-002159	1.27	MKG, FKG
14	Hapmap24717-BTC-002824	1.80	FKG
14	ARS-BFGL-NGS-59769	1.85	FKG
14	ARS-BFGL-NGS-24670	65.24	MKG
19	ARS-BFGL-NGS-39328	50.72	FKG
20	ARS-BFGL-BAC-27930	29.36	MKG
20	BTA-84181-no-rs	31.53	MKG
20	UA-IFASA-7069	31.91	MKG
27	ARS-BFGL-NGS-57448	36.47	MKG, PKG
29	ARS-BFGL-NGS-17707	45.96	MKG
29	ARS-BFGL-NGS-89746	48.83	MKG, PKG, MEY

Supplemental Table S4. Identified significant SNPs for for conformation traits

BTA	SNP name	Position SNP (Mb)	Trait
2	ARS-BFGL-NGS-109463	122.68	STAT
4	ARS-BFGL-NGS-112129	9.98	UD
4	Hapmap47436-BTA-88975	10.08	
5	BTA-11044-rs29016809	47.85	STAT
5	Hapmap49859-BTA-109537	82.33	BD
5	BTB-01278164	88.36	BCS, DCH, UD
5	Hapmap47397-BTA-74925	105.35	STAT
5	Hapmap60480-ss46526970	105.47	BD, STAT
5	ARS-BFGL-NGS-10549	105.51	STAT
5	ARS-BFGL-NGS-39379	105.78	STAT
6	ARS-BFGL-NGS-82008	85.90	BCS, CW, DCH
6	ARS-BFGL-NGS-112872	86.34	DCH
6	Hapmap54336-rs29010419	86.40	BCS, DCH
6	Hapmap54015-rs29022799	86.69	BCS
6	ARS-BFGL-NGS-48254	86.75	BCS, CW, DCH
6	ARS-BFGL-NGS-118182	86.86	BCS, CW, DCH, UD
6	BTB-00133212	86.92	BCS, CW, DCH, UD
6	ARS-BFGL-NGS-17376	87.09	BCS, CW, DCH, UD
6	BTA-68275-no-rs	87.27	BCS, CW, DCH, UD
6	BTA-22096-no-rs	87.59	BCS
6	BTB-00707501	88.33	BCS
7	ARS-BFGL-NGS-4774	16.18	STAT
8	UA-IFASA-8810	81.66	UD
8	Hapmap39282-BTA-63744	84.05	STAT
8	ARS-BFGL-NGS-212	84.21	STAT
11	Hapmap51861-BTA-86131	38.52	UD
11	ARS-BFGL-NGS-38413	78.08	STAT
11	ARS-BFGL-NGS-11105	78.44	STAT
11	ARS-BFGL-NGS-108206	79.11	STAT
11	Hapmap30206-BTA-126797	79.25	STAT, UD
11	BTA-99263-no-rs	79.41	STAT
18	ARS-BFGL-NGS-67312	18.13	BCS
19	BTB-00745293	28.12	UD
19	BTB-00745347	28.15	
19	ARS-BFGL-NGS-28940	28.90	STAT

Supplemental Table S5. Identified significant SNPs for metabolic diseases in first lactation

BTA	SNP name	Position SNP (Mb)	Trait
3	BTB-01948148	111.68	DA
10	ARS-BFGL-NGS-22303	18.25	DA
14	UA-IFASA-8135	26.89	META
17	ARS-BFGL-NGS-30992	28.95	META
26	ARS-BFGL-NGS-41148	123.69	DA

Supplemental Table S6. Identified significant SNPs for metabolic diseases in third lactation

BTA	SNP name	Position SNP (Mb)	Trait
2	ARS-BFGL-NGS-16745	71.44	KET
2	Hapmap32559-BTA-134272	84.97	KET
6	BTB-00133212	86.92	META
6	Hapmap58251-rs29024344	97.79	META
6	BTB-01095999	97.81	META
8	BTB-01582726	4.42	
8	BTA-86030-no-rs	4.50	KET
8	BTB-01990279	4.66	
17	BTB-01442839	43.74	MF
17	ARS-BFGL-NGS-93323	71.20	MF
23	ARS-BFGL-NGS-22482	14.53	MF